

Covid-19 infectiOn aNd medicineS In pregGNancy

Deliverable 7: CONSIGN-International Meta-analysis Protocol & Statistical Analysis Plan

Deliverable by the EU PE & PV Research Network under a Framework contract following procurement procedure EMA/2018/28/PE (Lot 4). Study on impact of COVID-19 infections and medicines in pregnancy (Specific Contract 04).

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List of abbreviations

ACCESS	vACCine covid-19 monitoring readinESS
ACOG	American College of Obstetricians and Gynaecologists
ADVANCE	Accelerated Development of VAccine beNefit-risk Collaboration in Europe
AESI	Adverse Event of Special Interest
ARDS	Acute respiratory distress requiring ventilation
ARS	Agenzia Regionale di Sanita' della Toscana
ATC	Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical
BMI	Body Mass Index
CDC	Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
CDM	Common Data Model
CI	Confidence interval
COVID-19	Coronavirus disease 2019
DAP	Data Access Provider
DDD	Daily defined dose
DNA	Desoxyribonucleic acid
DRE	Digital Research Environment
ECDC	European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control
ECMO	Extra-corporeal Membrane Oxygenation
EMA	European Medicines Agency
EMR	Electronic Medical Records
ENCePP	European Network of Centres for Pharmacoepidemiology and Pharmacovigilance
ETL	Extract, Transform, and Load
EU PAS	The European Union electronic Register of Post-Authorisation Studies
FICF	Catalan Institute of Pharmacology Foundation (FICF)
FISABIO-HSRU	Foundation for the Promotion of Health and Biomedical Research of Valencia Region - Health Services Research Unit
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GP	General Practitioner
IACS	Instituto Aragones de Ciencias de la Salud
ICD	International Classification of Diseases
ICU	Intensive Care Unit
LMP	Last menstrual period
mRNA	messenger Ribonucleic acid
NHS	National Health Service
ODHSI	Observational Health Data Sciences and Informatics
QC	Quality Control
SAIL	Secure Anonymised Information Linkage
SAP	Statistical Analysis Plan
SARS-CoV-2	Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus 2
SWANSEA	Swansea University
UiO	University of Oslo

1. Title

COVID-19 Infection and Medicines in Pregnancy (CONSIGN) International meta-analysis

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4. Deliverables and milestones

Deliverable	Date
D6. Description and characterization of the data sources to be included in the meta-analysis	16 January 2022
D7. Meta-analysis protocol and study analysis plan	18 April 2022
D8i. Interim report and manuscript including results of the meta-analysis (with all available data provided)	March 2023
D8f. Final report and manuscript including results of the meta-analysis	28 July 2023

Milestone	Date
Common Code Book to be shared with all the participating DAPs	February 2022
Statistical analysis plan	June 2022
Script for quality checks	July 2022
Data extraction & ETL	July 2022
Running quality & first analysis	September 2022
Interim report with available results	March 2023
Final report	July 2023

5. Background and rationale

5.1 Background

The pandemic of coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) is of particular concern for pregnant women. As pregnant women were not included in most of the clinical trials evaluating the effectiveness and safety of medications to treat and prevent COVID-19, there are significant gaps in knowledge about the effects of these treatments across all trimesters of pregnancy and their impacts on perinatal outcomes.¹ A recent systematic review published in October 2021 by Giesbers et al., reported on the pharmacological treatment of COVID-19 in pregnancy among six studies (599 women). The treatment included: antiviral treatment, (systemic) corticosteroids, antibiotics, and immunotherapy. In the review, the types and doses of the medications were not specified, and anticoagulation was not included. The number of pregnant women exposed to intervention was small despite the big denominators, hence it was not possible to do a meta-analysis and make any conclusions about pharmacological interventions for the treatment of pregnant women with COVID-19.¹

To our knowledge, there is no other meta-analysis in the literature to assess the impact of pharmacological treatment on pregnancy and neonatal outcomes. More insight is needed on the prevalence of the pharmacological treatments at the substance level used during pregnancy and their impacts on mothers, fetuses, and neonates. However, the analysis of the sole impact of medication on maternal and perinatal outcomes is complex since medicines were prescribed to patients presenting with the most severe disease and many confounding factors must be considered. Moreover, data sources cover either outpatients, or inpatients or both settings, which adds to the complexity of medication analysis.

5.2 What is already known from literature until February 2022?

The impact of COVID-19 medication on pregnancy outcomes may be confounded by several risk factors.

Pregnancy is associated with more severe COVID-19:

One US study found that pregnant women are at higher risk of becoming infected by COVID-19 and many studies demonstrated that pregnancy is associated with a higher risk of severe disease.^{2,3} In the meta-analysis of Allotey et al., (59 studies, 41 664 women), the odds of admission to an intensive care unit (odds ratio (OR) = 2.13, 95% confidence interval (95%CI): 1.53-2.95; $I^2 = 71.2\%$), invasive ventilation (OR = 2.59, 95%CI: 2.28-2.94; $I^2 = 0\%$), and need for extracorporeal membrane oxygenation (ECMO) (OR = 2.02, 95%CI: 1.22-3.34; $I^2 = 0\%$) were higher in pregnant and postpartum women than non-pregnant reproductive aged women.⁴ This association has been found especially in pregnant women after 20 weeks of gestation.⁵

Maternal comorbidity is associated with severe COVID-19, adverse maternal outcomes and intensive care unit admission related to COVID-19:

In the meta-analysis of Allotey et al., the following conditions were associated with severe COVID-19 in pregnancy:

- Maternal age over 35 years (OR = 1.83, 95%CI: 1.27-2.63; $I^2 = 43.4\%$)
- Obesity, defined as body mass index (BMI) over 30 kg/m² (OR = 2.37, 95%CI: 1.83- 3.07; $I^2 = 0\%$)

- Any pre-existing maternal comorbidity (OR = 1.81, 95%CI: 1.49-2.20; $I^2 = 0\%$)
- Chronic hypertension (OR = 2.00, 95%CI: 1.14-3.48; $I^2 = 0\%$)
- Pre-existing diabetes (OR = 2.12, 95%CI: 1.62-2.78; $I^2 = 0\%$)
- Pre-eclampsia (OR = 4.21, 95%CI: 1.27-14.00; $I^2 = 0\%$)⁴

In pregnant women with COVID-19, the same meta-analysis found that:

- Maternal age over 35 years is increased with admission to intensive care unit (ICU) (OR = 2.11, 95%CI: 1.69-2.63; $I^2 = 43\%$)
- BMI over 30 kg/m² is associated with ICU admission (OR = 2.71, 95%CI: 1.10-6.63; $I^2 = 63\%$), invasive ventilation (OR = 6.61, 95%CI: 1.98-22.02; $I^2 = 0\%$) and maternal death (OR = 2.27, 95%CI: 1.20-4.31; $I^2 = 0\%$)
- Non-western background is associated with ICU admission (OR = 1.66, 95%CI: 1.20-2.29; $I^2 = 35\%$), invasive ventilation (OR = 2.23, 95%CI: 1.25-3.97; one study) and maternal death (OR = 1.61, 95%CI: 1.05-2.47; $I^2 = 0\%$)
- Any pre-existing maternal comorbidity is associated with ICU admission (OR = 1.81, 95%CI: 1.49-2.20; $I^2 = 0\%$) and invasive ventilation (OR = 5.26, 95%CI: 1.76-15.68; $I^2 = 0\%$)
- Chronic hypertension is associated with ICU admission (OR = 4.72, 95%CI: 2.37-9.41; $I^2 = 13\%$), invasive ventilation (OR = 63.82, 95%CI: 9.69-420.45; $I^2 = 0\%$) and maternal death (OR = 4.25, 95%CI: 1.82-9.95; $I^2 = 0\%$)
- Pre-existing diabetes is associated with ICU admission (OR = 4.67, 95%CI: 1.94-11.22; $I^2 = 38\%$) and maternal death (OR = 14.88, 95%CI: 4.19-52.81; $I^2 = 53\%$)
- Pre-eclampsia is associated with admission to ICU (OR = 179.40, 95%CI: 7.69 to 4186.05; one study)⁴

The meta-analysis published by Lassi et al found that smoking was also associated with more severe disease (OR = 3.23, 95%CI: 1.67 to 6.25; $I^2 = 98\%$).⁵

Maternal comorbidity is associated with adverse maternal and pregnancy outcomes also in patients without COVID-19:

The following conditions are associated with the occurrence of acute maternal end-organ injury or maternal death (from the most predictive to the less predictive factor): severe preeclampsia/eclampsia, chronic congestive heart failure, pulmonary hypertension chronic ischemic heart disease, sick cell disease, multiple gestation, cardiac valvular disease, systemic lupus erythematosus, human immunodeficiency virus, mild or unspecified preeclampsia, drug abuse, placenta praevia, chronic renal disease, pre-existing hypertension, previous cesarean delivery, gestational hypertension, alcohol abuse, asthma, pre-existing diabetes mellitus, maternal age >44, between 40 and 44 years, and between 35 and 39 years. All these factors are included in the Bateman score.⁶ Maternal comorbidities, such as maternal age over 35 years and obesity are significantly associated with adverse pregnancy outcomes.^{7,8}

COVID-19 is associated with adverse pregnancy outcomes:

COVID-19 diagnosis is associated with an increased risk of pre-eclampsia (OR = 1.39, 95%CI: 1.29- 1.50; $I^2 = 25\%$), preterm birth (OR = 1.86, 95%CI: 1.34-2.58; $I^2 = 65\%$), stillbirth (OR = 1.46, 95%CI: 1.13-1.85; $I^2 = 17\%$) and cesarean delivery (OR = 1.67, 95%CI: 1.29-2.15; $I^2 = 95\%$). However, COVID-19 is not associated with miscarriage, preterm premature rupture of membranes, or operative delivery.⁹

COVID-19 is associated with adverse neonatal outcomes:

COVID-19 during pregnancy is associated with an increased risk of fetal distress (OR = 1.66, 95%CI: 1.35-2.05; $I^2 = 26\%$), low birth weight (OR = 1.69, 95%CI: 1.35-2.11; $I^2 = 0\%$), 5th minute Apgar score <7 (OR = 1.44, 95%CI: 1.11-1.86; $I^2 = 0\%$), and admission to neonatal intensive care unit (OR = 2.12, 95%CI: 1.36-3.32; $I^2 = 89\%$). However, COVID-19 during pregnancy is not associated with neonatal death.⁹

The delta variant of SARS-CoV-2 is associated with more severe COVID-19 infection:

Among obstetric patients of a US hospital in Alabama, proportions of severe and critical disease and ICU admissions were increased in the Delta cohort (July 2021 - August 2021) compared to the pre-Delta cohort (March 2020 - May 2021) (aOR = 2.76, 95%CI: 1.73-4.40). They also found that required respiratory support (aOR = 2.76, 95%CI: 1.73-4.40), intubation (aOR = 4.18, 95%CI: 2.06-8.48), and pharmacologic treatment (aOR = 2.31, 95%CI: 1.49-3.59) were also significantly increased in the Delta cohort compared to pre-delta cohort, after adjusting for asthma. Pharmacologic treatment included azithromycin, cephalosporins, remdesivir, dexamethasone, or convalescent plasma.

Rates of cesarean delivery, especially for maternal worsening status (aOR = 4.94, 95%CI: 1.90-12.88), preterm birth (aOR = 2.36, 95%CI: 1.68–3.32) and neonatal ICU admission (aOR = 1.77, 95%CI: 1.25-2.51) all increased in the Delta cohort.¹⁰ In Texas, pregnant women infected with the Delta variant had a higher risk of severe or critical illness when compared with the pre-delta epoch (11.8% versus 4.1%, aOR = 2.93, 95%CI: 1.18-7.69).¹¹ The UKOSS and NeTHOSS also compared severity of maternal disease and neonatal outcomes across different variants of the SARS-CoV-2 virus, with more severe maternal and perinatal outcomes during the periods when alpha and particularly delta variant was dominating as well as analyses of maternal risk factors associated with severe COVID-19.¹³⁻¹⁵

The impact of COVID-19 in pregnant women differs between high-income countries (HICs) and low-to-middle-income countries (LMICs):

Adverse pregnancy outcomes related to COVID-19 are more commonly seen in low-to-middle income countries (LMIC) compared to high income countries (HIC).¹⁶ The overall risk of adverse pregnancy outcomes is higher in LMICs compared to HICs (OR 2.53, 95%CI: 1.20-5.37; $I^2 = 96\%$). Maternal death (OR = 7.87, 95%CI: 4.90-13.16) and stillbirths (OR = 2.03, 95%CI: 1.17-3.57) are more common in LMICs. Preterm births and premature rupture of membranes are comparable in both groups. Neonatal deaths (OR = 3.77, 95%CI: 1.42-11.71) are more frequently reported in LMICs.¹⁶

COVID-19 vaccination is associated with less severe COVID-19 in pregnant women:

Vaccinated pregnant women had lower odds of severe or critical COVID-19 than non-vaccinated pregnant women in the US and European countries (aOR = 0.10, 95%CI: 0.01–0.49).^{12,13}

COVID-19 medication varies according to maternal comorbidity, COVID-19 severity, trimester of pregnancy, national guidelines, pandemic period, and vaccination status:

- *Heparin:*

In some national guidelines, prophylactic anticoagulation is prescribed in severe cases or in case of hospitalization for COVID-19.^{14,15} In other guidelines, the initiation of low molecular weight heparin (LMWH) and duration are discussed by a multidisciplinary team including hematologists, internists/intensivists and obstetricians, taking into account disease severity, the timing of delivery in relation to disease onset, whether the patient is admitted to the hospital or self-isolating at home, the

underlying prothrombotic risk secondary to comorbidities and the presence of major bleeding from obstetric or non-obstetric causes, including coagulopathies.¹⁶

- *Antivirals:*

Remdesivir: Initial studies suggested some benefit in shortening the median recovery time to 10 days [95%CI 9 to 11], as compared with 15 days [95% CI, 13 to 18] among those who received placebo. However, it has not shown any benefit in reducing mortality in the general population.¹⁷ The recommendations on remdesivir use in pregnant women differ between national guidelines. It is considered for compassionate use in Belgium, the US and UK.^{18,19}

Lopinavir-ritonavir: In patients admitted to hospital with COVID-19, lopinavir-ritonavir was not associated with reductions in 28-day mortality, duration of hospital stays, or risk of progressing to invasive mechanical ventilation or death.²⁰ After the results of the RECOVERY trial in June 2020, lopinavir-ritonavir has been shown to be ineffective and national guidelines recommended not to prescribe this association.^{20,21} From December 2020, WHO guidelines “recommend against” this drug for all patients with COVID-19, regardless of disease severity.¹⁸ Most national guidelines published by Obstetricians-gynecologists’ societies also consider that lopinavir-ritonavir should not be offered to pregnant women.¹⁹

Prevalence of antivirals: The meta-analysis published by Lassi *et al* found that the prevalence of antivirals use during pregnancy was associated with severe COVID-19 (OR=1.87 [1.47 to 2.37], I²=0%).⁶

- *Corticosteroids for maternal indication:*

Initially, there was a reluctance to use corticosteroids in patients infected with COVID-19 because of concerns with the progression of the infection due to reduced viral clearance, even prescribed for fetal lung maturation. In June 2020, the RECOVERY trial demonstrated that the use of steroids significantly reduced the mortality within 28 days as well as the duration of invasive ventilation in patients who required mechanical ventilation or oxygen supplementation.²² The Royal College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists in UK recommend using non-fluorinated corticosteroids for maternal severe COVID-19 to avoid fetal exposure. Thus, during pregnancy, if a preterm delivery is anticipated between 24⁺⁰ and 33⁺⁶ weeks of gestation, it is recommended to prescribe antenatal therapy with the usual doses of dexamethasone (4 doses of 6 mg given intramuscularly 12 hours apart) or betamethasone (2 doses of 12 mg given intramuscularly 24 hours apart) to induce fetal pulmonary maturation. In addition, this therapy should be followed by prednisolone (40 mg orally daily) or hydrocortisone (80 mg intravenously twice daily) to complete the maternal steroid course.¹⁹ In other countries, dexamethasone can be continued for a total of 10 days for maternal indication.^{15,23-25}

Prevalence of corticosteroids: The meta-analysis published by Lassi *et al* found that the prevalence of steroids use during pregnancy was not associated with severe COVID-19 (OR = 1.77, 95%CI: 0.86-3.65; I² = 0%).⁵

- *Antimalarials:*

Chloroquine and hydroxychloroquine could be prescribed in pregnant women only within a context of a clinical trial in pregnant women in some countries in Spring 2020.¹⁵ The RECOVERY trial in June 2020 demonstrated that hydroxychloroquine was ineffective in the general population.²⁶ Therefore, national

guidelines published by Obstetricians-gynecologists' societies recommend that it should no longer be prescribed.^{19,21}

- *Tocilizumab:*

The recommendations on tocilizumab use differ between national guidelines.¹⁹ Since July 2021, WHO recommends tocilizumab for the general population with severe or critical COVID-19.¹⁸ In the UK, tocilizumab (or sarilumab if unavailable) if needing escalation of care and/or if CRP>75. In the US, it is recommended not to prescribe or to have a discussion of the potential risks and benefits.^{18,19} Probably because there is almost no data on the efficacy and safety of tocilizumab and especially not for sarilumab in pregnant women.

- *Anti-SARS-CoV2 spike monoclonal antibodies:*

Since September 2021, WHO recommends the combination casirivimab-imdevimab for i) patients with severe COVID-19, under the condition that the patient has seronegative status; ii) patients with non-severe COVID-19, conditional to those at highest risk of hospitalization.²⁷ However, in January 2022, WHO predicted lack of efficacy for casirivimab-imdevimab with the omicron variant.

Testing policy and timing of test-positivity in pregnant women has an impact on COVID-19 severity:

There is evidence that testing strategy has an impact on the severity of disease found among pregnant women. Under non-universal testing, women with complications near delivery are more likely to be tested than women without complications, thereby inflating any association with adverse pregnancy outcomes compared with findings under universal testing. Irrespective of testing policy, women who test positive may also be followed more closely for complications and the threshold for medical interventions may be lowered.³³

The risk factors for severe COVID-19 infection, hospitalization, COVID-19 medication, and pregnancy outcomes already described in the literature and summarized previously are also illustrated in the directed acyclic graph (Figure 1) to give an overview of the confounding factors that we must consider in the analysis on the impact of COVID-19 medication on adverse pregnancy outcomes.

5.3 Rationale

Based on the final analysis of COVI-PREG data (CONSIGN WP2), interim analyses of INOSS data (CONSIGN WP3), and international literature, we know that use of medicines specific for COVID-19 in pregnant women is infrequent, highly correlated with severity of COVID-19 disease and changing over time since the start of the pandemic.¹

Since pregnant women have not been included in most clinical trials for COVID-19 medicines, there is an important gap in knowledge. In this context, regulators and other stakeholders need to be prepared for situations where questions arise regarding the impact of medicines used against COVID-19 during pregnancy, on maternal, pregnancy and neonatal outcomes.

The aim of our international meta-analysis is to describe the use of medicines to treat COVID-19 disease by trimester of pregnancy and the effects of medicines used to treat COVID-19 on maternal, pregnancy and neonatal outcomes and to pool as much data available around the world with similar protocols and settings. The Deliverable D6 describes the data sources that will be utilized and the in- and exclusion criteria.²⁸

Figure 1. Directed acyclic graph Illustration of the impact of COVID-19 medicines on pregnancy outcomes in COVID-19 infected pregnant persons

Legend: The directed acyclic graph was created with associations described in the literature, which have been detailed above. The directed acyclic graph was created with the DAGitty software for drawing and analyzing causal diagrams.²⁹

The color code is explained as follows:

- exposure
- outcome
- ancestor of exposure
- ancestor of outcome
- ancestor of exposure *and* outcome
- adjusted variable
- unobserved (latent)
- other variable
- causal path
- biasing path

To pool the available data, we will conduct two meta-analyses including prospective and retrospective data collection with reliable data on the different classes of these medicines and associated perinatal outcomes in a real-world clinical setting: the first combining population-based health care data sources (meta-analysis 1) and the second combining case-based registries compiled by health care professionals (meta-analysis 2).

6. Research questions and objectives

6.1 Research questions

The research questions are as follows: What is the use of medicines to treat COVID-19 in pregnant women and what are the effects on maternal, pregnancy and neonatal outcomes on a global level?

To answer the question, we will conduct two different meta-analyses, based on distinct types of underlying data (secondary use of existing data and primary case-based data collection).

6.2 Study objectives

The key objectives of CONSIGN-International are to describe and estimate:

- 1) Use of medicines to treat COVID-19 infection in pregnancy
- 2) The impact of COVID-19 on pregnancy and neonatal outcomes
- 3) Effects of medicines used to treat COVID-19 infection in pregnancy on pregnancy, perinatal and neonatal outcomes

7. Research methods

7.1 Flowchart for the selection process of data sources

CONSIGN Meta-analysis 1 (MA1) will pool the results of population-based health care data sources implementing the CONSIGN-WP1 protocol. CONSIGN Meta-analysis 2 (MA2) will pool the results of primary data collections on COVID-19 exposed pregnancies that are collected by health care facilities. The flowchart of the selection process of studies and data sources is shown in Figure 2. The detailed description of the selected participating data sources is available in CONSIGN deliverable 6.²⁸

Figure 2. Flowchart describing the data sources/study selection process, the left trajectory displays the MA1 and the right trajectory displays the MA2

In CONSIGN meta-analysis 1, each of the studies is using data collections that have been initiated independently. For this, we have selected sites that use EHR data and have completely or partially implemented the CONSIGN WP1 protocol. Since the submission of deliverable 6, there are 8 study sites in CONSIGN WP1 instead of 9. The Leibniz Institute for Prevention Research and Epidemiology - BIPS group in Germany will not participate in the project. They are not able to provide necessary data during pandemic period due to long lag time.

In CONSIGN meta-analysis 2, each of the studies is using data collections that have been initiated during the start of the pandemic. For this, we have selected sites that have collected data on patients in a structured manner during health care visits in health care facilities and have followed the pregnant women till delivery.

7.2 Harmonization

To harmonize the semantics of the data, we have reviewed the protocols, code books and definitions on population, exposure, covariates, and outcomes across the included sites, and mapped the variables. To further align we propose this SAP as a guidance to the way that the analysis will be conducted and semantically harmonized.

For the meta-analysis 1, we share with the sites the shell tables, the code lists for outcomes and exposures, as well as covariates, and the definitions of risk windows, trimester calculations and other algorithms. No R-scripts will be provided, as study sites perform the analysis themselves. Each site will provide the completed shell tables according to the shared definitions. These shell tables will be the starting point for the meta-analysis/pooling.

For the meta-analysis 2, we created a mapping of the variables that are collected in each of the sites, which allows for a mapping and a recoding (syntactic and semantic harmonization), which will allow us to send an R-script that will allow for the running of the analysis locally. Only the aggregated results of the R-script will be shared for pooling on the Digital Research Environment at UMC Utrecht. These R-outputs will be the starting point for the meta-analysis/pooling.

7.3 Meta-analysis 1 combining studies using health care data sources

7.3.1 Specific objectives

The specific objectives for CONSIGN-International meta-analysis 1 are based on the CONSIGN WP1 protocol and analysis plans and are:

1. Assess and compare the prevalence of medication use used in pregnant women with COVID-19

The specific objectives are:

- a) To estimate the prevalence of medicine use in pregnant women with COVID-19
- b) To compare prevalence of medicine use between pregnant women with COVID-19 with those for pregnant women without COVID-19
- c) To compare prevalence of medicine use between pregnant women with COVID-19 and non-pregnant women of reproductive age with COVID-19.

2. Severity and clinical outcomes of COVID-19 disease in pregnant women and non-pregnant women with COVID-19

The specific objective is:

- a) To describe the severity of COVID-19 disease in pregnant women and non-pregnant women with COVID-19

3. Rates of relevant pregnancy and neonatal outcomes

The specific objectives are:

- a) To describe the rate of adverse outcomes between pregnant women with and without COVID-19
- b) To assess the impact of COVID-19 on pregnancy-related adverse outcomes
- c) To describe the rate of adverse outcomes between pregnant women with COVID-19 according to medication use among non-hospitalized women with COVID-19 in pregnancy

All medication use refers to outpatient prescribed/dispensed medications as recorded in the electronic health care registries participating in the project.

7.3.2 Study design

The participating sites/networks will follow the study design of CONSIGN WP1, whose protocol was made available in [EUPAS39438](#). The CONSIGN WP1 study is a retrospective, multi-database, dynamic cohort study, conducted during the years 2018 to 2020 or latest availability, including a period of SARS-CoV-2 circulation in Europe until the date of last data availability for each data source.

The source population includes women of reproductive age (12-55 years), pregnant women and their children observed in one of the participating data sources for at least one day during the study period (01.01.18 – 31.12.20/last data availability).

Studying the outcomes of pregnancy and identifying pregnancies is subjected to left and right censoring. Several time varying variables need to be considered, pregnancies last 9 months before outcomes can be measured and many data sources identify pregnancies based on end of pregnancy. Figure 3 shows how the left and right censoring operate.

Left censoring is caused by the study start date, 1/1/2018. To avoid left censoring bias for pregnancy analyses we will only include pregnancies that coincide with the pandemic (C, D). Although specified in the protocol we will not include A and B, since these would be historic non-COVID pregnancies, and we wish to have contemporaneous controls.

Right censoring of pregnancies is a more important concern, any data cut that does not capture full information up until October 2021, will suffer from right censoring. Since data sources identify pregnancies based on pregnancy end, shorter follow-ups would select preterm births. Therefore, the first analysis will have bias on all pregnancies for which the end cannot be observed prior to the data cut.

Figure 3. Schematic illustration of pregnancy cohorts considering SARS-COV-2 circulation. In brown: the group of non-pregnant women with COVID-19. For the analyses we will include women in group C and D (pregnant women), as well as non-pregnant women of childbearing age (contemporaneous) and the historical comparator group (B).

7.3.3 Data sources in meta-analysis 1

The identified networks and data access providers (DAPs) who agreed to participate are:

- CONSIGN WP1 includes 8 data sources in 7 European countries.
 - Denmark – nationwide registries
 - France – nationwide registries
 - Italy – regional registry (Tuscany)
 - Norway – nationwide registries
 - Spain – regional registries (Valencia and Aragon)
 - Sweden – nationwide registries
 - UK – national registry (Wales)
- Sentinel system (FDA- Harvard Pilgrim)
- CAMCCO (Canadian provinces: Alberta, Manitoba, Quebec, +/- Ontario)

Table 1 displays the characteristics of the 3 data sources. A more extensive description of the separate data sources can be found in [CONSIGN D6](#), Table 3.³⁵

7.3.4 Study population

The study cohort consists of two pandemic populations and one population of historical controls, which may vary per objective.

- Pregnant women (aged 12-55 years) whose pregnancy overlapped the COVID-19 pandemic

This includes women who were 12-55 years of age and pregnant on the start date of the pandemic, defined as 1/3/2020 for the European countries and 1/2/2020 in Canada, or their pregnancy started

after this date, and whose pregnancy prompted a recording in the data sources by the time of most recent update with a green, yellow, or blue classification by the pregnancy algorithm (see below).

Table 1. Description of three data sources included in the meta-analysis on EHR databases

Data source	Expected number of pregnant women with COVID-19	Period of data covered	In/out patients	Medicines	Outcomes	Potential inclusion biases
CONSIGN WP1	Unknown	From 2018 to end of 2021	Out	ATC-level 2 (+/- ATC-level 5) Dispensing or prescribing date considered as timing of medication use	Maternal, pregnancy and neonatal outcomes	None
Sentinel system (FDA- Harvard Pilgrim)	Approximately 10,000	From Jan 1, 2020-present (lag time varies by Data Partner, currently about 3-5 months)	In + out	Outpatient pharmacy claims using National Drug Codes (NDC)	Maternal, pregnancy and neonatal outcomes	Only live births, publicly insured people may be underrepresented, and uninsured people are not represented
CAMCCO	5,780 (approximate estimation considering 1.7% of COVID positive pregnant women)	1996-2021	In + out	ATC-level 2 (+/- ATC-level 5) Medical and Pharmacy Insurance Claims – outpatient and inpatient calendar date, name of drug (DIN), dosage, duration	Maternal, Pregnancy, neonatal	No bias detected so far

We will use the IMI-[ConcePTION pregnancy algorithm](#) which allows for various streams of information to detecting pregnancies and their start or end date:

- Quality is green if both pregnancy_start_date and pregnancy_end_date are recorded;
- Quality is classified yellow if pregnancy_end_date is recorded as the record date and pregnancy_start_date is imputed
- Quality is blue if pregnancy_start_date is recorded and pregnancy_end_date is imputed;
- Quality is red if both pregnancy_start_date and pregnancy_end_date are imputed;

Only green (based on registers) yellow and blue pregnancies will be included in the analyses, women with red pregnancies are excluded from the non-pregnant group.

Other exclusions:

1. Pregnancies that were started before June 1, 2019 (and would end before the start of the pandemic in Europe (defined as 1/3/2020))
2. Pregnancies in women with less than one year of continuous data prior to the start of pregnancy.

The analyses will be conducted at the level of the trimester of pregnancy. Only trimesters coinciding with the pandemic period (1/3/2020 in Europe and 1/2/2020 for Canada) and later, and before the end of data availability) are eligible for inclusion.

A woman can contribute data on more than one pregnancy, and more than one trimester, during the study period. Women who participate with multiple pregnancies will be handled as individual pregnancies in the analyses, given the low numbers.

- Non-pregnant women of childbearing age during COVID-19 pandemic

For each pregnancy identified in the pregnant cohort among women with COVID-19, three comparator episodes (among women aged 12-55 years), will be selected to compare medical product use, as well as baseline characteristics during a defined period for which a woman did not have a pregnancy.

Pregnant women with COVID-19 in pregnancy during the pandemic will be matched (1:3 without replacement) to non-pregnant women diagnosed with COVID-19 on age group and calendar week of COVID-19 diagnosis. (NOTE: a caliper may be used to extend calendar time matching). Non-pregnant women will use the start date of pregnancy of their matched pregnant partner. Therefore, three matched pregnant and non-pregnant cohorts will be created with COVID-19 diagnosis in the three different trimesters.

- Historical comparator group: Pregnant women whose pregnancy was completed prior to the COVID-19 pandemic

This includes women who were 12-55 years of age and whose pregnancies commenced from 01.01.2018 and were completed prior to 01.01.2020, and whose pregnancy prompted a recording in the data sources by the time of most recent update with a green, yellow, or blue classification by the pregnancy algorithm (see above).

Only WP1 and CAMCCO have data on historical controls. They will present prevalence estimates of adverse pregnancy and neonatal outcomes for women whose pregnancy was completed prior to the start of the pandemic (2018/2019). This will not be a matched analysis but provide relevant baseline rates that will be valuable to discussed in the final report. FDA/Sentinel are not presenting historical baseline rates of adverse pregnancy outcomes. FDA restricts to a matched analysis between women+-COVID-19 whose pregnancies aligned time wise during the pandemic.

7.3.5 SARS-CoV-2 and COVID-19 severity

Exposures of main interest are SARS-CoV-2 infections and COVID-19, which will be identified by recordings in surveillance systems or diagnostic codes health care records (Annex 1) and/or laboratory results. COVID-19 was not widely tested in the first wave and has increased over time. Therefore, misclassification may be highest during January-June 2020, especially for non-severe COVID-19. Regulations for coding in ICD9 may have been specified later in time.

COVID-19 disease severity will be categorized into two levels: non-severe and severe, based on whether the woman is admitted. In the protocol we aimed to estimate distinctions in severity of COVID-19 during hospitalization, but this is not accurately measurable.

- Non-severe COVID-19: Recording of a positive COVID-19 test (PCR or antigen test) or COVID-19 diagnosis, with no subsequent hospital admission with a recording (primary or secondary) of COVID-19 (within a 4-week period).
- Severe COVID-19: Any recording of 'COVID-19 positive test', or 'COVID-19 complication' in any of the diagnostic fields in hospital records, not just the principal diagnosis. Except: if the COVID-19 test positive test is +/- 3 days of delivery date/hospitalization for obstetric reasons & no codes of severe symptoms (pneumonia, respiratory aid/use of ventilator) is found subsequently. These episodes will be re-classified as non-severe.

Note: For WP1, the women who have been hospitalized for delivery or obstetric complications and who have been screened positive for COVID (routine screening for hospitalized patients), even though they were asymptomatic or paucisymptomatic, may induce a misclassification bias: these women tested positive could be misclassified as severe instead of non-severe COVID. WP1 will add an additional step in the analyses to handle this potential misclassification bias:

1. Flag the women tested positive for COVID between the 3 days before and the 3 days after the delivery
2. Check other codes during the time of the hospitalization, such as pneumonia and other codes related to severe COVID.
3. Then reclassify them as non-severe or severe episodes.

CAMMCO will also follow the same steps to avoid misclassification of pregnant women admitted for their delivery and who are screened positive for COVID but have few or no symptoms and would not have been hospitalized for COVID-19.

For Sentinel, the information is available for reliable classification according to COVID-19 severity (any recorded diagnosis (non-severe), hospitalization for COVID-19 as the primary diagnosis, hospitalization for COVID-19 diagnosis with an ICU admission...).

7.3.6 Medicines

Medications are exposures of interest as they may impact pregnancy outcomes, be used to treat symptoms of COVID-19 infections or be proxies for maternal medical conditions (risk factors for adverse outcomes). Timing of medication use relative to COVID-19 as well as timing of medication use in pregnancy (trimester), is relevant to understand drug utilisation patterns (objective 1) as well as for maternal and pregnancy outcomes (objective 3).

Information on medication will be retrieved from outpatient or primary care prescription/dispensing records. All medication use refers to outpatient/ primary care prescribed/dispensed medications as recorded in the data banks of the data sources participating in the project. For each prescription/dispensing record we will assume the prescription/dispensing date to reflect timing of actual medication availability.

The prevalence of medication use of special relevance for COVID-19 will be examined in the 30-day window pre- and post- COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis for WP1 and CAMCCO analyses (or 90 days pre

and post infection for Sentinel analyses already done for objectives 1a,1b,1c). Medication will be analyzed at ATC-2, ATC-3 level and where relevant to substance level (ATC-level 5).

The medicines presented in the Table 2 (and Annex 2) are all those used to treat COVID-19 during the period 2020-2021 and mentioned in the WHO "Therapeutics and COVID-19" living guidelines, including potential applicability in pregnant persons and in the NIH guidelines, including special considerations for pregnancy.^{18,30}

In Table 2 on medicines used to treat COVID-19, the distinct levels of the Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical levels are described:

- ATC second level: therapeutic subgroup
- ATC third level: pharmacological subgroup
- ATC fourth level: chemical subgroup
- ATC fifth level: chemical substance

The codes from the Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical Classification system of the medicines were those available on March 17th, 2022, from the website of WHO Collaborating Centre for drugs Statistics Methodology and Norwegian Institute of Public Health: https://www.whocc.no/atc_ddd_index/

Maternal vaccinations beyond COVID-19 vaccines will be considered a covariate: Influenza A-H1N1, Pneumococcal disease, Pertussis.

7.3.7 Maternal, pregnancy and neonatal outcomes

Maternal, pregnancy and neonatal outcomes of interest are listed in Table 3.

7.3.8 Co-variates

Covariates of interest are listed in Tables 4.

Table 2. Exposure variables of interest: medicines used to treat COVID-19

ATC-level 2 of medication groups of special relevance to COVID-19	ATC-level 2-code	ATC-level 3 -name	ATC-level 3 -code	ATC-Level 4 -name	ATC-Level 4 -code	ATC-level 5 name	ATC level-5 code
Drugs used in diabetes	A10						
Antithrombotic agents	B01	Antithrombotic agents	B01A	Heparin group	B01AB	enoxaparin (Low molecular weight heparin)	B01AB05
						heparin (unfractionated)	B01AB01
				Platelet aggregation inhibitors, excluding heparin	B01AC	acetylsalicylic acid	B01AC06
Antihypertensives	C02, C03, C04, C07, C08 and/or C09						
Corticosteroids for systemic use	H02	Glucocorticoids for systematic use, plain	H02A	Glucocorticoids	H02AB	dexamethasone	H02AB02
						betamethasone	H02AB01
						hydrocortisone	H02AB09
						methylprednisolone	H02AB04
						prednisone	H02AB06
Antibacterials for systemic use	J01	Beta-lactam antibacterials, penicillins	J01C	Penicillins with extended spectrum	J01CA	amoxicillin	J01CA04
						ampicillin	J01CA01
						ampicillin, combinations	J01CA51
				Combination of penicillins, including beta-lactamase inhibitors	J01CR	piperacilline + tazobactam	J01CR05
						ampicillin and beta-lactamase inhibitor	J01CR01
						amoxicillin and beta-lactamase inhibitor	J01CR02
		Other beta-lactam antibacterials (J01D)	J01D	First generation cephalosporins	J01DB	cefalexin	J01DB01
						cefazolin	J01DB04
				Second generation cephalosporins	J01DC	cefuroxime	J01DC02
						Third-generation cephalosporins	J01DD
				ceftazidime	J01DD02		
				ceftriaxone	J01DD04		
cefixime	J01DD08						
cefodizime	J01DD09						

				Fourth-generation cephalosporins	J01DE	cefepime	J01DE01
				Carbapenems	J01DH	meropenem	J01DH02
		Macrolides, Lincosamides and Streptogramins	J01F	Macrolides	J01FA	azithromycin	J01FA10
						clarithromycin	J01FA09
						erythromycin	J01FA01
				Lincosamides	J01FF	clindamycin	J01FF01
		Aminoglycoside antibacterials	J01G	Other aminoglycosides	J01GB	amikacin	J01GB06
						gentamicin	J01GB03
		Other antibacterials	J01X	Glycopeptide antibacterials	J01XA	vancomycin	J01XA01
						teicoplanin	J01XA02
Antimycotics	J02						
Antimycobacterials	J04						
Antivirals for systemic use	J05	Direct acting antivirals	J05A	Nucleosides and nucleotides excl. Reverse transcriptase inhibitors	J05AB	remdesivir	J05AB16
				Antivirals for treatment of HIV infections, combinations	J05AR	lopinavir-ritonavir	J05AR10
				Neuraminidase inhibitors	J05AH	oseltamivir	J05AH02
				Antivirals for treatment of HCV infections, combinations	J05AP	ribavirin	J05AP01
				/	/	molnupiravir	No ATC code available
				/	/	nirmatrelvir	No ATC code available
				Other antivirals	J05AX	favipiravir	J05AX27
Immune sera and globulins	J06	Immunoglobulins	J06B	Antiviral monoclonal antibodies	J06BD	casirivimab-imdevimab (anti-SARS-CoV2 mABs)	No ATC code available
						tixagevimab-cilgavimab (anti-SARS-CoV2 mABs)	No ATC code available
						bamlanivimab, bamlanivimab + etesevimab	No ATC code available
						sotrovimab (anti-SARS-CoV2 mABs)	No ATC code available
				/	/	plasma of convalescent	No ATC code available
				/	/	plasma of convalescent	No ATC code available
				Immunoglobulins, normal human	J06BA	IV Immunoglobulins	J06BA02
Vaccinations	J07	Viral vaccines	J07B	Other viral vaccines	J07BX	Covid-19 vaccines	J07BX03

Antineoplastic agents	L01	Protein kinase inhibitors	L01E	BCR-ABL tyrosine kinase inhibitors	L01EA	imatinib	L01EA01
				Janus-associated kinase (JAK) inhibitors	L01EJ	ruxolitinib	L01EJ01
Immunostimulants	L03	Immunostimulants	L03A	Interferons	L03AB		
Immunosuppressants	L04	Immunosuppressants	L04A	Selective immunosuppressants	L04AA	baricitinib	L04AA37
						tofacitinib (kinase inhibitor)	L04AA29
				Interleukin inhibitors	L04AC	tocilizumab (IL6 receptor blockers)	L04AC07
						sarilumab (IL6 receptor blockers)	L04AC14
						anakinra (Interleukin-1 Inhibitors)	L04AC03
Calcineurin inhibitors	L04AD	ciclosporin	L04AD01				
Anti-inflammatory drugs	M01						
Antigout preparations	M04	Antigout preparations	M04A	Preparations with no effect on uric acid metabolism	M04AC	colchicine	M04AC01
Analgesics	N02	Other analgesics and antipyretics	N02B	Anilides	N02BE	paracetamol	N02BE01
Psycholeptics	N05						
Psychoanaleptics	N06	Antidepressants	N06A	Selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors	N06AB	fluvoxamine	N06AB08
Antiprotozoals	P01	Agents against amoebiasis and other protozoals diseases	P01A	Nitroimidazole derivatives	P01AB	metronidazole	P01AB01
				Other agents against amoebiasis and other protozoals diseases	P01AX	nitazoxamide	P01AX11
		Antimalarials	P01B	Aminoquinolines	P01BA	chloroquine	P01BA01
				hydroxychloroquine	P01BA02		
Anthelmintics	P02	Antinematodal agents	P02C	Avermectines	P02CF	ivermectine	P02CF01
Nasal preparations	R01						
Medicines for obstructive airway disease	R03						
Cough and cold preparations	R05						

Table 3. Outcomes of interest meta-analysis 1

OUTCOMES	Definition	Identification of outcomes in the common data model *	Link to code list
Maternal outcomes			
Maternal death	Maternal death or maternal mortality is defined by the World Health Organization (WHO) as "the death of a woman while pregnant or within 42 days of termination of pregnancy, irrespective of the duration and site of the pregnancy, from any cause related to or aggravated by the pregnancy or its management but not from accidental or incidental causes	Maternal date of death during pregnancy or in the six weeks (42 days) after resolution of the pregnancy, OR diagnostic codes	Annex 3
Preeclampsia	The Brighton Collaboration defines preeclampsia as follows: Preeclampsia is a clinical syndrome characterized by <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pregnancy ≥ 20 weeks AND <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New onset hypertension (systolic blood pressure ≥ 140 mmHg and/or diastolic blood pressure ≥ 90 mmHg) sustained on two measurements over a minimum of 1h AND <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New onset proteinuria 	Recording of 'pre-eclampsia' in registry data, OR diagnostic codes	Annex 4
Gestational diabetes	The Brighton Collaboration defines gestational diabetes as follows: Gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM) is a clinical syndrome characterized by the absence of pre-gestational diabetes diagnosis defined by <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Previous diagnosis of diabetes while not pregnant OR <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First trimester hemoglobin A1c level of ≥ 6.5% OR <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First trimester fasting blood glucose 126 mg/dL or 6.93 mmol/L AND <p>Identification of sustained hyperglycaemia during pregnancy not due to other known causes (i.e., corticosteroids, beta-mimetics, etc.)</p>	Recording of 'gestational diabetes' in registry data, OR diagnostic codes	Annex 5
Pregnancy outcomes			
Spontaneous abortion	Pregnancy ending spontaneously before 22 weeks of gestation (i.e., up to and including 21 6/7 weeks of gestation)	Recording of 'spontaneous abortion' in registry data, OR diagnostic codes	Annex 6
Termination of Pregnancy for Fetal Anomaly (TOPFA)	TOPFA can be structural malformations, syndromes and chromosomal anomalies performed for.	Diagnosis code for suspected fetal anomaly (Annex 7) followed by diagnostic code for planned/induced abortion (Annex 8), OR recording of 'TOPFA' in registry data	Annex 7&8
Caesarean section	Delivery of foetus via abdominal incision (laparotomy) and then uterine incision (hysterotomy)	Recording of 'caesarean section' in registry data, OR diagnostic codes	Annex 9
Preterm birth	WHO defines preterm birth as any birth before 37 completed weeks of gestation, or fewer than 259 days since the first day of the woman's last menstrual period (LMP). This is further subdivided based on gestational age: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • extremely preterm (<28 weeks) • very preterm (28–<32 weeks) • moderate or late preterm (32–<37 completed weeks of gestation). 	Duration of pregnancy < 37 weeks, OR diagnostic codes	Annex 10
Stillbirth	Stillbirth definition from the Brighton collaboration: Stillbirth is a foetal death occurring before birth after a selected predefined duration of gestation. The death of the foetus could have occurred before onset of labour (antepartum) or at the delivery (intrapartum).	Recording of 'stillbirth' in registry data, OR diagnostic codes	Annex 11

	WHO/ICD defines stillbirths as the death of a foetus that has reached a birth weight of 500 g, or if birth weight is unavailable, gestational age of 22 weeks or crown-to-heel length of 25 cm. There are several definitions for the minimal gestational age: WHO/ICD/EMA = 22 WG, ACOG/CDC = 20 WG, UK = 24 WG.		
Neonatal outcomes			
Neonatal death	Neonatal death refers to death of a live-born baby within the first 28 days of life. Early neonatal mortality refers to the death of a live-born baby within the first seven days of life, while late neonatal mortality refers to death after 7 days until before 28 days.	Based on date of death of neonate within 28 days of date of birth (Neonatal death will be identified based on dates of death in the PERSONS table, or from a variable in the birth registries).	No Annex
Low birth weight	Body weight of the newborn at birth of less than 2,500 grams (up to and including 2,499 g).	Recording of child's weight less than 2,500 gram in registry data OR diagnostic codes.	Annex 12
Small-for-gestational age (SGA)/ Intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR)	Based on Brighton Collaboration: Fetal growth restriction (FGR) is a common complication during pregnancy. It refers to a fetus that has failed to reach its biological growth potential because of placental dysfunction. It is difficult to diagnose, because of the variability in clinical presentation. Small for gestational age (SGA) is not the same as FGR. SGA is not caused by placental dysfunction, it can either be a constitutionally small fetus without any pathological causes or other causes can be congenital malformations or infections. By using a Doppler, it is possible to distinguish between FGR and SGA. An abnormal umbilical artery Doppler in early pregnancies (<32 weeks) and an abnormal middle cerebral artery Doppler in late pregnancies (>32 weeks) are related to FGR. The definition for fetal growth restriction can be divided in different levels.	Raw z-score based on baby's weight, gestational age and gender, in registry data, OR diagnostic codes	Annex 13
Low Apgar score (5-minute)	A 5-minute Apgar score of 7–10 is classified as normal, a score of 4–6 as moderately abnormal, and a score of 0–3 as low in the term infant.	Recording of Apgar score at 5 minutes as 0-3 in registry data OR diagnostic codes	Annex 14
Admission in NICU	Admission of the neonate to a highly intensive care ward		No Annex
Major congenital anomalies	<p>Major congenital anomalies' definition from the Brighton collaboration: Congenital anomalies are conditions of prenatal origin that are present at birth, potentially impacting an infant's health, development and/or survival. Anomalies which affect an infant's life expectancy, health status, physical or social functioning may be described as "major" anomalies. Examples include cleft lip and spina bifida. Major structural anomalies are the conditions that account for most of the deaths, morbidity and disability related to congenital anomalies. Congenital anomalies might occur in isolation (single defect) or as a group of defects (multiple defects) which are often part of well-described associations (e.g., VACTERL). One or more congenital anomalies are estimated to occur in 3% of pregnancies.</p> <p>Below is the case definition of major congenital anomalies by Brighton Collaboration. Because the group of conditions comprising "Congenital Anomalies" is quite diverse, they divided them into three groups:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. External structural defects (e.g., cleft lip or gastroschisis) 2. Internal structural defects (e.g., congenital cardiac defects or intestinal atresias) 3. Functional defects (e.g., galactosemia or Gaucher's disease). 	Recording of major congenital anomalies in registry data OR diagnostic codes within the first 3 months of life	Annex 15 (Note: all codes lists will be combined in one, we will not report on individual anomalies)

	<p>For all levels of diagnostic certainty counts that a major congenital anomaly is a structural or functional defect with the following three characteristics:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Of prenatal origin 2. Present at the time of live birth or fetal demise, or in utero 3. Affecting (or has the propensity to affect) the health, survival, or physical or cognitive functioning of the individual <p>The majority of structural congenital anomalies are diagnosed before 2 years of age, usually within the first 6 months of life.</p>		
Microcephaly	<p>Brighton Collaboration: Congenital microcephaly, also referred to as primary microcephaly due to its presence in utero or at birth, is a descriptive term for a structural defect in which a fetus or infant's head (cranium) circumference is smaller than expected when compared to other fetuses or infants of the same gestational age, sex and ethnic background. Congenital microcephaly can be diagnosed either postnatally or prenatally and is usually defined by the measurement of occipital-frontal circumference (head circumference) that is more than 2 standard deviations (SDs) below the mean for age and sex or less than the 3rd percentile for age and sex. Severe microcephaly is defined as head circumference more than 3 SDs below the mean for age and sex.</p>	Recording of microcephaly in registry data OR diagnostic codes within the first 3 months of life	Annex 16

* This column is specific to WP1 (common data model)

NA: not available

Table 4. Covariates of interest meta-analysis 1

Covariate	Definition	Link to codes/algorithms
Age	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 12-24 years of age • 25-39 years of age • 40-55 years of age <p>When numbers are low, 12-24 can be combined with 25-39</p>	Date of Birth
Trimester of pregnancy*	<p>For WP1: The American College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists (ACOG) definition of timing in pregnancy will be used:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Trimester 1: from Last Menstrual Period (LMP) to day 97 after LMP; or end of pregnancy, whichever earlier 2. Trimester 2: from day 98 after LMP to day 195 after LMP; or end of pregnancy, whichever earlier 3. Trimester 3: from day 196 after LMP onwards until end of pregnancy <p>Pregnancy start and end dates will be assessed from medical birth registers for those data sources with access to a registry, while existing algorithms for defining start and end of pregnancy will be utilized in those data sources with an existing algorithm, novel algorithms will be developed if they do not exist to limit bias. Start of pregnancy is date of last menstrual period (LMP), end of pregnancy is the date of delivery or abortion (elective/spontaneous). The period of pregnancy will be divided into trimesters, start of trimesters will also be labelled with the calendar month during the pandemic time period. We will also use the Conception algorithms to predict condition of pregnancy in women whose pregnancy has not ended. LMP: The first day of the LMP is estimated by subtracting the gestational age at delivery from the pregnancy</p>	No Annex, will be based on start date of pregnancy

	<p>end date. Due date, and thus, gestational length and LMP, is estimated by ultrasound, and only if unavailable, by the woman's recall of LMP.</p> <p>For Sentinel:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. First trimester: days 0 to 90 of gestation (13 weeks) 2. Second trimester: days 91 to 180 (13+1 to 25+5 weeks) 3. Third trimester: days 181 ($\geq 25+6$ weeks through the day of the hospital admission for live-birth delivery). <p>For CAMCCO:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. 1st trimester: 0-98 days (> 0 to ≥ 14 weeks gestation) 2. 2nd trimester: 99-182 days (> 14 to ≥ 26 weeks' gestation) 3. 3rd trimester: ≥ 183 days ($\geq 26+1$ weeks' gestation to end of the pregnancy) 	
Covid-19 positive test or diagnosis	Recording of a positive COVID-19 test (PCR or antigen test), or presence of a diagnostic code in health care records	Annex 1
At-risk medical conditions for severe COVID-19	<p>Cardiovascular disease/serious heart conditions include heart failure, coronary artery disease, cardiac myopathies, hypertension</p> <p>Sickle Cell Disease</p> <p>Chronic lung disease including COPD, cystic fibrosis, severe asthma, interstitial lung disease, pulmonary hypertension, bronchiectasis,</p> <p>Type 1 & 2 Diabetes</p> <p>Obesity diagnosis or having a BMI ≥ 30 kg/m²</p> <p>Chronic kidney disease</p> <p>Chronic liver disease diagnosis (cirrhosis, non-alcoholic fatty liver disease, alcoholic liver disease, autoimmune hepatitis)</p> <p>HIV</p> <p>Immunosuppression & solid organ transplants</p> <p>Cancer</p> <p>Mental health disease (depression, dementia, and schizophrenia spectrum disorders)</p>	Annex 17 for diagnosis codes and medicines proxies in Annex 2
Risk conditions for obstetric complications	<p>Prior maternal history of gestational diabetes or pre-eclampsia</p> <p>Prior: stillbirth or late miscarriage, small for gestational age (SGA) child or fetal growth restriction (FGR), congenital anomaly.</p>	Annex 4, 5, 6, 11, 13, 15
Severity of COVID-19 disease	<p>Non-severe COVID-19: Recording of a positive COVID-19 test (PCR or antigen test) with no subsequent hospital admission with a recording of COVID-19</p> <p>Severe COVID-19: Any recording of 'COVID-19 positive test', or 'COVID-19 complication' in any of the diagnostic fields in hospital records, not just the primary discharge diagnosis (WHO level 2-5). Except: if the COVID-19 test positive test is +/- 3 days of delivery date/hospitalization for obstetric reasons & no codes of severe symptoms (pneumonia, respiratory aid/use of ventilator) is found subsequently. These episodes will be re-classified as non-severe.</p>	Annex 1
Calendar month of COVID-19 diagnosis	March 2020 till [according to each DAP]	Based on date of diagnosis/positive test

* The definitions of trimesters of pregnancy are slightly different among the 3 partners. For Sentinel, the start date of pregnancy is often imputed using the assumption of a full-term pregnancy. For CAMCCO, there are historical reasons as to why the trimesters are classified in that manner but not clear as to the source. The suggestion is to leave these minor differences as is.

7.3.9 Analyses to be performed at study sites

Objective 1a: Prevalence of medication use in the pregnant study population with COVID-19

Population: Study population includes all pregnant women (aged 12-55 years) whose pregnancy overlapped the pandemic and had a diagnosis of/positive test results for COVID-19 during pregnancy.

Exposure: COVID-19 in pregnancy (overall, severe, and non-severe), stratified by trimester for the pregnant women.

Analyses: Medicines, identified by outpatient or primary care prescribing/ dispensing codes will be described by therapeutic classes (ATC-level 2) and if possible, individual drugs (ATC-level 5). The numerator will be the number of women having one or more items dispensed/prescribed (date of prescribing/dispensing) of the specific medication within the given time-period (30 days pre- and 30 days post- COVID-19 positive test or diagnosis) (90-day window for Sentinel). The denominator will be the number of women contributing at least one day of person-time to that trimester. Table shells 1a-1c will be filled (Annex 18).

Objective 1b: Matched comparison of exposure to medication between pregnant women with and without COVID-19

Population: Pregnant study population includes all pregnant women (aged 12-55 years) whose pregnancy overlapped the pandemic. Pregnant women with COVID-19 in pregnancy during the pandemic will be matched (1:3 without replacement) to pregnant women without COVID-19 in pregnancy during the pandemic. Matched pregnant women without COVID-19 will have estimated pregnancy start within +/- 14 days from pregnancy start for pregnant women with COVID-19 and have same age category. The index date is the date of positive COVID-19 test. Pregnant women without COVID-19 will use the date of the matched partner's COVID-19 positive test or diagnosis. Therefore, three matched cohorts for pregnancies with and without COVID-19 will be created with a COVID-19 diagnosis in the three different trimesters. For the referent pregnant cohort without COVID-19, additional exclusion criteria will be applied requiring no COVID-19 diagnosis was observed during any trimester (i.e., for the entire pregnancy period) and user specified pre-pregnancy period.

Exposure: COVID-19 in pregnancy, stratified by trimester of infection.

Analyses: This comparison will be conducted using a matched analysis of cohorts of pregnant women with and without COVID-19. Baseline characteristics will be described between the matched groups (table shells 2a-2c, Annex 18). Comparisons of baseline characteristics between severe and non-severe COVID will be conducted using standardized differences. Prevalence of medication use in the 30 days prior to the COVID-19 infection and in the 30 days after the index date of COVID-19 will be computed in the sub-cohort of pregnant women diagnosed with COVID-19 and in the sub-cohort of pregnant women not diagnosed with COVID-19 during pregnancy. A 90-day window will be used by Sentinel. The numerator will be the count of women having one or more dispensing/prescription (date of prescription/dispensing) of the specific medication within the time window pre/post COVID-19 positive test or diagnosis. The denominator will be the number of women contributing person-time to that trimester. The results will be presented by trimester of infection, and the severity of COVID-19 disease. (See shell tables 2d-f, Annex 18).

Objective 1c: Matched comparison of exposure to medicines between pregnant and non-pregnant women with COVID-19

Population: Pregnant study population includes all pregnant women (aged 12-55 years) whose pregnancy overlapped the pandemic and had a diagnosis of COVID-19 during pregnancy. Pregnant women with COVID-19 in pregnancy during the pandemic will be matched (1:3 without replacement) to non-pregnant women diagnosed with COVID-19 on age group and calendar week of COVID-19 diagnosis. (NOTE: a caliper may be used to extend calendar time matching). Non-pregnant women will use the start date of pregnancy of their matched pregnant partner. Therefore, three matched pregnant and non-pregnant cohorts will be created with COVID-19 diagnosis in the three different trimesters.

Exposure: COVID-19 in pregnant vs. COVID-19 in non-pregnant women.

Analyses: This comparison will be conducted using a matched analysis of cohorts of pregnant women with COVID-19 and non-pregnant women with COVID-19. Baseline characteristics will be described between the matched groups (table shells 3a-3c, Annex 18). Comparisons of baseline characteristics between severe and non-severe COVID will be conducted using standardized differences. Prevalence of medication use in the 30 days prior to the COVID-19 infection and in the 30 days after the index date of COVID-19 will be computed in the sub-cohort of pregnant women diagnosed with COVID-19 and in the sub-cohort of non-pregnant women diagnosed with COVID-19. A 90-day window will be used by Sentinel. The numerator will be the count of women having one or more dispensing/prescription (date of prescription/dispensing) of the specific medication within the time window pre/post COVID-19 positive test or diagnosis. The denominator will be the number of women contributing at least one day of person-time to that trimester. The results will be described by trimester of infection, and the severity of COVID-19 disease. (See shell tables 3d-3f, Annex 18).

Objective 2: Severity of COVID-19 disease in pregnant women and non-pregnant women with COVID-19.

Population: Pregnant and non-pregnant women with COVID-19.

Exposure: COVID-19 in pregnant vs. COVID-19 in non-pregnant women, stratified by trimester of infection for the pregnant women.

Analysis: Severity of COVID-19 disease will be categorized into two levels: non-severe and severe COVID-19, based on whether the woman is admitted to hospital with a COVID-19 diagnosis. The original aim was to compare the association between medication use and the severity of COVID-19 but since we do not have in hospital use of medicines, this will not be analyzed. Furthermore, since severity of COVID-19 is so highly correlated with the type and number of medicines used, analysis is futile. Instead, for all analyses, the results of prevalence of medication use will be presented stratified by disease severity (non-severe COVID-19 vs. severe COVID-19). Tables (See shell tables 1b-1c; 2a-2f; 3a-3f, Annex 18).

Objective 3a. Prevalence of adverse maternal and pregnancy outcomes in pregnant women in the pre-pandemic era (WP1 and CAMCCO only)

Population: Historical comparator group of pregnant women who were 12-55 years of age and whose pregnancies commenced from 01.01.2018 and were completed prior to 01.01.2020.

Analysis: The prevalence of each pregnancy-related outcome will be computed as the number of events divided by the number of pregnant women in the cohort. Results will be tabulated as in Annex 18 shell table 4.

Objective 3b: Matched comparison of adverse maternal and pregnancy outcomes between pregnant women with and without COVID-19

Population: The study population for this analysis will comprise the same matched pregnant study cohort as for objective 1b but will be restricted to subjects where there is a time span of at least 40 weeks from LMP to end date of data available (Table 5). To negate the risk of closed cohort bias; the latest start date of pregnancy needs to be a full 40 weeks before the end date of data available, as any data extraction that does not capture full information up until the end date of data available will suffer from right censoring. Since many data sources identify pregnancies based on pregnancy end, shorter follow-ups would select preterm births.

Exposure: COVID-19 in pregnancy (overall, severe, non-severe), stratified by trimester of infection.

Analysis: Adverse pregnancy and neonatal outcomes in pregnant women with COVID-19 will be described by presenting the prevalence overall, by trimester of pregnancy at COVID-19 diagnosis, and

by COVID-19 severity. The prevalence of each pregnancy-related outcome will be computed as the number of events divided by the number of pregnancies in the cohort stratified by trimester of COVID-19 infection. This count will differ depending on the outcome of interest. For example, neonatal death, will only include live born infants in the denominator. Effect estimates will be calculated as prevalence ratios and prevalence differences with 95% CIs using a modified Poisson model with robust estimate of the variance, while adjusting for co-variates. To avoid immortal time bias when studying effect of COVID-19 infection on risk of non-live birth outcome (i.e. spontaneous abortion, stillbirth), exposure will be modelled as time-dependent within the Cox proportional hazard framework. In each model, adjustments will be made for age, risk factors for severe COVID-19 and obstetric risk factors. Results will be tabulated as in Annex 18 shell table 5a to 5o.

Objective 3c: Prevalence of adverse outcomes according to medicines use in pregnancy among women with COVID-19 in pregnancy but not hospitalised for COVID-19

Population: Pregnant women with COVID-19 (where there is a time span of at least 40 weeks from LMP to end date of data available) without a hospital admission for COVID-19*. The population will be restricted to women categorized as having non-severe COVID-19 to avoid misclassification of medicines exposure during hospitalisation, as we lack information on exposures to medication in hospitals.

Exposure: Medication exposure will be defined at three levels:

- Exposed to medication in the 30 days pre COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis
- Not-exposed to medication in 30 days post COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis
- Exposed to medication in the 30 days post COVID-19 positive test/diagnosis

Analysis: The prevalence of individual outcomes will be presented per level of medication exposure, stratified by trimester of infection. Tables will be filled for each outcome (See Table 6a, Annex 18 as an example).

* Diagnosis for COVID-19 will not include those indicative of past COVID-19 infection, such as 'history of COVID-19', 'personal history of COVID-19', 'post-COVID-19 syndrome', 'sequel of COVID-19'.

Table 5. Outcome-specific risk window for inclusion of pregnant women in the corresponding analysis

Outcome	Pregnancies included	Exposure window ¹	Modelling	Comment
Maternal death	All pregnancies	From LMP to 42 days post pregnancy end	No modelling due to small numbers.	
Gestational diabetes	Pregnancies that reached at least 20 weeks of gestational age	First trimester	Modified Poisson regression model ²	Outcome has a date restriction (occurs after gestational week 22). Because the operational definition of gestational diabetes is any outcome occurrence from start of second trimester, only exposure in the first trimester time window is investigated.
Pre-eclampsia (including eclampsia & HELLP)	Pregnancies that reached at least 20 weeks of gestational age	First trimester	Modified Poisson regression model	Outcome has a date restriction (occurs after gestational week 22). Because the operational definition of pre-eclampsia is any outcome occurrence from start of second trimester, only exposure in the first trimester time window is investigated.
Termination of Pregnancy for	All pregnancies	First trimester	Modified Poisson regression model	

Fetal Anomaly (TOPFA)				
Caesarean section	All pregnancies	From LMP to end of follow up	Modified Poisson regression model	
Pre-term birth	Live births only	From LMP to before week 37 of gestation	Modified Poisson regression model	Outcome has a date restriction (occurs before gestational week 37). Hence, exposure up to end of gestational week 36 window is investigated.
Neonatal death	Live births only	From LMP to end of follow up	Modified Poisson regression model	
Low birth weight	Live births only	From LMP to end of follow up	Modified Poisson regression model	
Small-for-gestational age (SGA)/ Intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR)	Live births only	From LMP to end of follow up	Modified Poisson regression model	
Low Apgar score (5-minute)	Live births only	From LMP to end of follow up	Modified Poisson regression model	
Admission in NICU	Live births only	From LMP to end of follow up	Modified Poisson regression model	
Major congenital anomalies	All pregnancies ³	First trimester	Modified Poisson regression model	
Microcephaly	All pregnancies	First trimester	Modified Poisson regression model	
Spontaneous abortion	All pregnancies	From LMP to week 22 of gestation ⁴	Extended Cox regression model	Outcome has a date restriction (occurs before gestational week 22). Hence, exposure up to gestational week 22 window is investigated. Modelling of time to event is necessary to avoid immortal time bias.
Stillbirth	Pregnancies that reached at least 22 weeks of gestational age ⁴	From LMP to end of follow up	Extended Cox regression model	Outcome has a date restriction (occurs after gestational week 22). Modelling of time to event is necessary to avoid immortal time bias.

¹ COVID-19 positive test or diagnosis.

² Effect estimates will be calculated as prevalence ratios or prevalence differences with 95% CIs using a modified Poisson model with robust estimate of the variance, while adjusting for co-variates.

³ DAPs may do this differently. Ideally the denominator should be all pregnancies (GVP III), However non-live births (greater than gestational week 12) tend to be rare and constitute a small proportion of pregnancies.

⁴ DAPS may do this differently.

7.3.10 Meta-analysis

In the first stage, a summary statistic will be calculated for each study site, to describe the observed prevalence of medications, adverse maternal, pregnancy and neonatal adverse outcomes and association risks in the same way for every study, based on the shell tables.³¹ In the second stage, a summary (combined) effect estimate is calculated as a weighted average of the effects estimated in the individual studies.

We will use forest plots to show individual point estimates (95% confidence intervals) for each data source, and a diamond to represent the pooled point estimate (95% CI) for each outcome of interest.

As we do not expect a fixed effect due to differences in source data and sizes, a random-effects model will be used for pooling.³¹ The combination of intervention effect estimates across studies may optionally incorporate an assumption that the studies are not all estimating the same intervention effect but estimate intervention effects that follow a distribution across studies. We will evaluate heterogeneity with the I^2 statistic. If the I^2 value is 40% or greater, we will consider heterogeneity to be present.

Heterogeneity will be explored to test the stability of findings across different study designs and different approaches to both exposure ascertainment and selection of study participants. Such sensitivity analyses should alert us to inconsistencies and prevent misleading conclusions.³²

In the Sentinel data source, only pregnancies with live births are included. It is an important inclusion bias that we need to address. This limitation will primarily impact the neonatal outcomes, but also to a lesser extent obstetric and maternal outcomes as patients with late miscarriage or stillbirth have a higher risk of presenting with adverse maternal and pregnancy outcomes at the same time. Sensitivity analyses will be performed with and without Sentinel data to highlight this inclusion bias and adapt the analyses if necessary.

Regarding the difference in time-window of medications prescription captured in Sentinel, 90-days window versus 30-days window in CONSIGN WP1 and CAMCCO, sensitivity analysis will be performed with and without Sentinel.

7.4 Meta-analysis 2 combining studies using case-based-registries

7.4.1 Specific objectives

The specific objectives for CONSIGN-International meta-analysis 2 are based on the COVI-PREG (WP2) and INOSS (WP3) CONSIGN protocol and analysis plans and are:

- 1) To estimate the prevalence of medicines used for COVID-19 treatment in pregnant women diagnosed with COVID-19, stratified by trimester of pregnancy and maternal disease severity.
- 2) To assess the risk of relevant maternal, pregnancy and neonatal outcomes associated with medicines used for COVID-19 treatment during pregnancy.

7.4.2 Study design

Participating sites/networks have primary data collections on COVID-19 exposed pregnancies that are collected by/in health care facilities. In each of the participating sites a case-control study will be conducted, and these results will be pooled.

Cases are defined as pregnant women with a SARS-CoV-2 positive test (polymerase chain reaction or antigenic test) and an adverse maternal outcome/pregnancy outcome/neonatal outcome. Controls will be pregnant women with a SARS-CoV-2 positive test without adverse maternal outcome/pregnancy outcome/neonatal outcome.

7.4.3 Data sources in meta-analysis 2

The identified networks and registries who agreed to participate are:

- COVI-PREG (CONSIGN WP2)
- INOSS (CONSIGN WP3)
- SET-NET (CDC)
- George Washington meta-analysis
- Saudi-FDA

Table 6 displays the characteristics of the 5 data sources. A more extensive description of the data sources can be found in [CONSIGN D6](#).²⁸

The five registries have qualitative information available on inpatients and outpatients' medicines used around the COVID-19 positive period or test and maternal and perinatal outcomes. We already know from the final report of COVI-PREG that 10.4% of pregnant women infected with COVID-19 received medicines against COVID-19 until July 1st, 2021. We also know from the interim report of INOSS that prophylactic anticoagulation was given to 41.7% of pregnant women with COVID-19, but between 0 and 10% for the other medications in 2020. In SET-NET, 15.2% of the pregnant women infected with COVID-19 received COVID-19 specific treatment, with remdesivir prescribed most frequently (57%) (Table 6).

7.4.4 Study population

Inclusion criteria: Eligible for inclusion are pregnant women identified in antenatal care of health care facilities with a positive test for SARS-CoV-2 at any point during pregnancy using RT-PCR and/or antigen tests between January 1, 2020, and December 31, 2020 / June 2022 (different study ends according to DAPs described in table 6), and at least follow-up until two days after delivery. Only pregnancies with a reported pregnancy outcome will be included.

Exclusion criteria:

- Data collections on self-reported pregnancies are not included because of the risk of selection and misclassification.
- Pregnant women who are under the age of majority in their jurisdiction, who have not given their informed consent to have their health data stored anonymously for research purposes, or who are not able to consent for themselves.

- To avoid the inclusion bias due to the earlier outcomes occurrence for preterm births we will exclude all cases, even already delivered, that will not have completed theoretical gestational age of 42 weeks at the time of analysis (which corresponds to the post-term gestational age when almost all pregnancies are delivered). It means that an already premature delivered patient, who has a post-term date later than the analysis date will be excluded.

Table 6 Description of the 5 data sources included in the meta-analysis on registries databases

Data source	(Period of data covered	In/out patients	Number of patients (%) who received any medication to treat COVID-19
COVI-PREG, WP2	3,370	March 25, 2020 - June 2022 (delivery date)	In + outpatients	205/1964 (10.4%) between 25th March 2020 and 1st July 2021
INOSS, WP3	2,347	March - December 2020 (delivery date)	Only inpatients	Antibiotic single: 467 (19.9%) Antiviral single: 36 (1.5%) Antibiotic + antiviral: 32 (1.4%) Hydroxychloroquine: 133 (5.7%) Steroids maternal: 196 (9.5%) Anti-IL6: 0 (0) IVIg: 0 (0) Prophylactic anticoagulation: 926 (41.7%) Curative anticoagulation: 61 (3.2%)
SET-NET (CDC)	At least 14,806 in 2020	2020 and some 2021 (infection date)	In + outpatients	Among 2020 infections, of 1,732 pregnant people with moderate-to-critical illness and sufficient medial record abstraction to determine presence or absence of maternal treatment, 22.9% received treatment, with 15.2% receiving a COVID-19 specific treatment. The most common COVID-19 specific treatments were remdesivir (57%), dexamethasone (45.8%), and azithromycin with hydroxychloroquine (15.4%)
George Washington MA	At least 4,111	2020 and some 2021 (infection date)	In + outpatients	NA
Saudi-FDA	2,200	March 2020 - October 2021	In + outpatients	NA

NA: not available yet

7.4.5 SARS-CoV-2 and COVID-19 severity

A COVID-19 diagnosis corresponds to a positive SARS-CoV-2 RT-PCR and/or antigen test.

The maternal disease severity is classified according to the WHO scale as follows:

- Not severe: any recorded diagnosis (level 1 according to WHO classification)
- Severe: hospitalization for COVID-19 (confirmed or suspected) and over (levels 2-3-4-5 according to WHO classification)

7.4.6 Medicines

The exposure of interest are all the medicines administered to treat COVID-19, its related symptoms and the medications used to prevent its complications, accounting from positive SARS-CoV-2 test until 30 days after. For instance, antibiotics prescribed for a urinary infection before the COVID-19 episode should not be considered. Prophylactic anticoagulation during hospitalization or at home 2 weeks after COVID-19 must be considered. Each medicine will be a dichotomous variable (yes, no, unknown or missing). Information on exact dose and the duration of treatment is not captured.

Like meta-analysis 1, all medicines used to treat COVID-19 presented in Table 2 are captured. Availability of each of the medicines for the 5 data sources can be found in the codebook (Annex 19).

7.4.7 Maternal, pregnancy and neonatal outcomes

Maternal, pregnancy and neonatal outcomes of interest are listed in Table 7. They will be analyzed individually and as part of a composite outcome. Availability of each of the outcomes for the 5 data sources can be found in the codebook (Annex 19). The 3 composite adverse outcomes include at least one of the individual outcomes as follows:

Maternal composite outcome

Cases with adverse maternal outcomes will be defined as patients with at least one of the following criteria:

- ICU admission during hospitalization for COVID-19 (WHO level 3)
- Acute respiratory distress requiring ventilation during hospitalization for COVID-19 (WHO level 4)
- Invasive ventilation
- ExtraCorporeal Membrane Oxygenation (ECMO)
- Maternal death during hospitalization for COVID-19 (any cause) (WHO level 5)

Pregnancy composite outcome

Cases with adverse pregnancy outcomes will be defined as patients with at least one of the following criteria:

- Miscarriage
- (Pre)-eclampsia diagnosed after COVID-19 diagnosis
- Gestational diabetes diagnosed after COVID-19 diagnosis
- Termination of pregnancy for congenital malformation diagnosed after COVID-19 infection
- Intrapartum/emergency cesarean section
- Preterm birth
- Stillbirth

All these pregnancy outcomes should occur after the COVID-19 event to be considered as outcomes.

Neonatal composite outcome

Cases with adverse neonatal outcomes will be defined as patients with at least one of the following criteria:

- Neonatal death

- Neonatal intensive care unit (NICU) admission
- Birthweight <10th for gestational age (based on INTERGROWTH 21st tables)
- Presence of a major congenital anomaly
- Microcephaly

For multiple gestations if only one of the neonates fulfills the adverse outcome criteria, it will count as one case. This means we will count each neonate separately.

7.4.8 Co-variates

Availability of the covariates for each data source can be found in the Codebook (Annex 19). Two variables will be created to take into account 2 potential confounding factors: the quality of care that can be different for each study site, and high-risk pregnancy which more likely to be associated with adverse maternal, pregnancy and neonatal outcomes.

- Quality of care

Quality of care will be categorized according to the level of income of the country of delivery. The level of income according to the World bank 2020-2021 classification includes 4 categories: high income / upper middle / lower middle / low income and will be used.³³ However, instead of 4 categories, we will use a dichotomous variable in our analysis: high income level versus middle- and low-income level. The country of delivery will be considered the same as the country of residence.

- High risk pregnancy

At least one of the following variables:

- Maternal age over ≥ 35
- Pre-existing hypertension or diabetes
- Congenital or chronic heart disease, chronic renal disease, pulmonary disease, auto-immune disease, HIV
- Obesity (BMI > 30)
- Multiple pregnancy (considering the current pregnancy with COVID-19 event)
- (Pre)-eclampsia (before diagnosis of COVID-19)
- Previous cesarean section
- Previous stillbirth

Table 7. Outcomes of interest meta-analysis 2

Outcomes	Definition	Reference
Maternal outcomes		
ICU admission related to COVID-19	ICU admission in a patient with COVID-19 related admission (WHO level 3)	WHO
Invasive ventilation	Invasive mechanical ventilation is defined as the delivery of positive pressure to the lungs via an endotracheal or tracheostomy tube	
Extra-Corporeal Membrane Oxygenation (ECMO)	A life support system that circulates the blood through an oxygenating system. ECMO may be used to treat acute respiratory distress syndrome or irreversible heart failure.	
Acute respiratory distress requiring ventilation during hospitalization for COVID-19	Acute respiratory distress requiring ventilation during hospitalization for COVID-19 (WHO level 4)	WHO
Maternal death during hospitalization for COVID-19	Maternal death during hospitalization for COVID-19 (any cause): "the death of a woman while pregnant or within 42 days of termination of pregnancy, irrespective of the duration and site of the pregnancy" (WHO level 5)	WHO
Pregnancy outcomes		
Miscarriage (synonym spontaneous abortion)	Pregnancy ending spontaneously before 22 weeks of gestation (i.e. up to and including 21 6/7 weeks of gestation)	(Definition according to each study site is accepted)
Preeclampsia	Pre-eclampsia is a complex medical disorder; world-wide, each year, it is responsible for over 500,000 fetal and neonatal deaths and over 70,000 maternal deaths. Pre-eclampsia can deteriorate rapidly and without warning; we do not recommend classifying it as 'mild' or 'severe'. Proteinuria is not mandatory for a diagnosis of pre-eclampsia. Rather, this is diagnosed by the presence of de novo hypertension after 20 weeks' gestation accompanied by proteinuria and/or evidence of maternal acute kidney injury, liver dysfunction, neurological features, hemolysis or thrombocytopenia, and/or fetal growth restriction. Pre-eclampsia may develop or be recognised for the first-time intra-partum or early post-partum in some cases	ISSHP classification (Definition according to each study site is accepted)
Gestational diabetes mellitus	Gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM) is defined as glucose intolerance diagnosed after the first trimester of pregnancy and usually recognized at 24 to 28 weeks of gestation on the basis of abnormal glucose tolerance testing.	(Definition according to study site is accepted)
Termination of Pregnancy for Fetal Anomaly (TOPFA)	Termination of pregnancy for congenital malformation diagnosed after COVID-19 infection	
Cesarean section	Delivery of fetus via abdominal incision (laparotomy) and then uterine incision (hysterotomy)	
Preterm birth	Birth at less than 37 completed weeks (less than 259 days) of gestation	
Stillbirth	Delivery of a dead fetus after 22 weeks of gestation Other commonly reported subgroups: - Antepartum or during pregnancy or "macerated" - Intrapartum, defined as no signs of life at delivery and more than 500 g or >22 weeks of gestation, with intact skin and no signs of disintegration in utero. The death is assumed to have occurred in the 12 h before delivery and to be more likely due to an intrapartum event.	WHO
Neonatal outcomes		
Neonatal death	Neonatal mortality refers to death of a live-born baby within the first 28 days of life, regardless of gestational age. Early neonatal mortality refers to the death of a live-born baby within the first seven days of life, while late neonatal mortality refers to death after 7 days until before 28 days.	WHO
Low birth weight	Body weight of the newborn at birth of less than 2,500 grams (up to and including 2,499 g).	
Small-for-gestational age (SGA)/ Intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR)	Birthweight below the 10 th percentile according to INTERGROWTH 21 curves	INTERGROWTH-21st ³⁴
Low Apgar score (5-minute)	A 5-minute Apgar score strictly below 7 at 5 minutes (between 0 and 6)	
Admission in NICU	Admission of the neonate to a highly intensive care ward	
Neonatal COVID-19 diagnosis	Positive SARS-CoV-2 RT-PCR test and/or antigen test in the neonate	
Major congenital anomalies	Morphological, functional and/or biochemical developmental disturbance in the embryo or foetus whether detected at birth or not. The term congenital anomaly is broad and includes congenital abnormalities, foetopathies, genetic diseases with early onset, developmental delay. Both onset and diagnosis of congenital anomalies can be delayed. A life-threatening structural anomaly or one likely to cause significant impairment of health or functional capacity and which needs medical or surgical treatment.	ICD-10 codes according to meta-analysis 1 on EHR
Microcephaly	Infant's head circumference < 2 SD or definition according to the local charts	

7.4.9 Analyses to be performed at study sites

Table 8 gives an overview of the different analyses per objective of meta-analysis 2. The Shell tables for the analyses are attached in Annex 20.

A detailed description of the data for the five data sources providing counts, percentages for categorical variables and distributions for continuous variables will be provided.

Shell tables 1a and 1b (Annex 20) will provide baseline characteristics of pregnant women diagnosed with COVID-19 by trimester of infection and by severity. All characteristics will be assessed at time of infection (time zero). Shell tables 3, 5 and 7 provide description and associations between baseline characteristics (including trimester of infection and COVID-19 severity) of pregnant women and maternal, pregnancy and neonatal outcomes. Odds ratios (OR) and their 95% confidence intervals will be described for each maternal and pregnancy characteristics and maternal, pregnancy and neonatal outcomes.

Table 8 Overview of analyses per objective of meta-analysis on case-based registries

Objective	Study design	Cohort	Outcome	Exposure	Stratification	Statistical method	Estimator
1	Cohort	Pregnant women with COVID-19	Medication groups Adverse maternal, pregnancy and neonatal composite outcomes	Substance level and ATC-2 levels, depending on the number of cases	Trimester of pregnancy, COVID-19 severity	Descriptive Univariate analysis	Prevalence and 95% CI Prevalence ratio (OR and 95% CI)
2	Case control	Pregnant women with COVID-19	Adverse maternal, pregnancy and neonatal composite outcomes	Medication at the substance level and ATC-2 levels	Stratification according to COVID-19 severity	Univariate analysis Multivariate logistic regression analysis	Odds ratio (OR and 95% CI) Adjusted OR (95% CI)

The first aim is a descriptive analysis to describe medicines' use. The prevalence of medicines used for COVID-19 treatment in pregnant women diagnosed with COVID-19 will be described with numbers, percentages, and confidence intervals, stratified by trimester of pregnancy that COVID-19 was diagnosed and maternal disease severity (Annex 20, Shell tables 2a and 2b respectively).

The stratification according to maternal COVID-19 severity will be binary:

- Severe COVID-19, defined as WHO classification at least at level 2: hospitalization related to COVID-19 (for SET-NET: hospitalization during pregnancy, except for delivery)
- Non severe COVID-19, defined as WHO classification level 1 (any recorded diagnosis)

Standardized differences will be calculated for comparisons of baseline characteristics between groups.

The second aim is to describe the outcomes of the pregnancies and to assess the association between medicines used for COVID-19 treatment during pregnancy among pregnant women with a SARS-CoV-2 positive test, and adverse maternal, pregnancy and neonatal outcomes.

The association between each medication at ATC-level 2 and the substance level (ATC-level 5) and maternal, pregnancy and neonatal outcomes will be assessed using univariate analyses, stratifying by severity of COVID-19. Categorical variables will be compared by Chi-square tests or Fisher's exact tests as appropriate. Crude Odds ratios (OR) and their 95% confidence intervals will be described for each medicine and maternal, pregnancy and neonatal outcomes.

Finally, the association between each medication at ATC-level 2 (and at the substance level depending on the number of cases) and maternal, pregnancy and neonatal outcomes will be assessed using multivariate logistic regression, according to 2 models:

- Model 1: adjusted for trimester of infection
- Model 2: adjusted for covariates significantly associated with maternal, pregnancy or neonatal outcomes in univariate analysis

Adjusted Odds ratios (aOR) and their 95% confidence intervals will be described for each medicine and maternal, pregnancy and neonatal outcomes. These results will be presented in shell tables 4a to 4e for maternal outcomes, 6a to 6h for pregnancy outcomes and 8a to 8i for neonatal outcomes (Annex 20).

It is highly likely that the confounding covariates included in the model 2 will differ according to the study sites. It will be discussed in 1-1 meetings with each study site after the univariate analyses and before the multivariable analyses to find an agreement for the covariates to be included in Model 2.

7.4.10 Meta-analysis

Participating sites will be requested to transform their data into the common data model according to the codebook presented in Annex 19. In order to produce the required output each site will first receive the quality checks (paragraph 8.2), and subsequently the data transformation scripts. The R-scripts will create the output required for the descriptive shell tables (see Annex 20). All data will be summarized by site, on a count/descriptive level.

For the estimation of effect sizes of medicines, we will use a hybrid approach

- 1) Sites share data in the common data model on the DRE, where it will be analyzed
- 2) Sites run the analytical scripts locally, and will share aggregate data or effect estimates only

Data/estimates on the DRE will be transformed into forest plots to show individual site point estimates (95% confidence intervals) for each data source, and a diamond to represent the pooled point estimate (95% CI) for each outcome of interest.

As we do not expect a fixed effect due to differences in source data and sizes, a random-effects model will be used.³¹ The combination of intervention effect estimates across studies may optionally incorporate an assumption that the studies are not all estimating the same intervention effect but estimate intervention effects that follow a distribution across studies. Heterogeneity will be assessed with the I^2 statistic. If the I^2 value is 40% or greater, we will consider heterogeneity to be present.

The statistical analyses will be performed with the R software (Package 'meta' a General Package for Meta-Analysis, Version: 5.2-0, date: 2022-02-04).

8. Data management

8.1 Data quality

To fulfill the CONSIGN aim, we will assess the quality of the datasets according to IMI ConcePTION- data characterization principles which comprises of 3 levels of quality checks (completeness, logic, benchmarking).

Quality Check Level 1:

The first one is considering completeness, which will be investigated by describing the distribution and missing values as absolute number and proportion (in %).

Quality check Level 2

The second level check will be making sure the data is logical. We will operationalize this by assessing the logical relationship and consistency between variables providing similar information. This analysis will concern only a few variables because of the branching logic used in the data collection platform to avoid mismatch between variables (e.g., the question "Invasive ventilation? Yes/No" is only available for patients who have a positive answer to the question "Inpatient management: ICU admission? Yes/No")

Quality check Level 3

Level 3 data check will focus on comparisons across sites, benchmarking with reference to external data and will be focused on examining the data distribution trends over time (by examining output by year and year/month of each selected event). An analysis of the enrolment rate will be performed for the participating study sites which are including pregnant women from different countries (i.e., COVI-PREG, INOSS and George Washington meta-analysis) or different states of the US (SET-NET / CDC). The analysis of the enrolment rate of each participating site will be added to the report to contextualise the results.

The responsibility of the quality check levels will be shared between CONSIGN group and the partners for their own data.

8.2 Data sharing

For CONSIGN WP1, data management follows the ConcePTION model and pipeline.

For the international meta-analysis 1, sites will be requested to fill the shell tables as presented in Annex 20. Data will be post-processed on the Digital Research Environment and pooled.

For the international meta-analysis 2, the DAPs will provide results based on a shared R-script that runs on a common data model.

- Common data model

For the common data model, we created a mapping of the variables that are collected in each of the sites and a required common format (Annex 19), which allow for a mapping and a recoding (syntactic and semantic harmonization), which will allow us to send an R-script for the running of the analysis locally.

- Quality check

The statistical analyses will be performed with the R software version 4.2.0 (2022-04-22). An R script will be developed to allow for harmonized analysis across all the initiatives, based on a common data model of variables.

The R-script for the 3 quality check levels will be coded by a CONSIGN researcher (MD, MPH at the University of Bern, Switzerland) on R version 4.2.0.

First, the R-script will be tested on the dataset extracted from the COVI-PREG registry in June 2022. Second, it will be double checked by the data analysts in University Medical Center Utrecht (UMCU), the Netherlands. Third, it will be re-run on the COVI-PREG and INOSS datasets. Then, the R-code for the 3 quality check levels will be sent to the participants of the meta-analysis 2 in order that they run their individual analyses on their site. The participants will send the output of their quality checks to the Digital Research Environment in Utrecht. Only aggregated results will be shared and uploaded to the DRE at UMC Utrecht for further pooling.

- Statistical analyses: first round

All the statistical analyses of objective 1 will be performed.

Concerning objective 2, univariate analyses will be performed on baseline characteristics of pregnant women diagnosed with COVID-19 and their association with maternal, pregnancy and neonatal adverse outcomes (Annex 20, tables 3,5 and 7 respectively).

One to one online meetings between partners and CONSIGN group will be organized to discuss the interim results and the next steps.

- Statistical analyses: second round

In the multivariable logistic regressions, the model 2 will be adjusted for covariates associated with maternal outcomes in univariate analyses (Annex 20, tables 4a to 4e, 6a to 6h, 8a to 8i). It is highly likely that the confounding covariates included in the model 2 will be different according to the study sites. Therefore, the R scripts for the second round will be different for each study site.

The responsibility of the statistical analyses will be shared between CONSIGN group and the partners for their own data.

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